

Addendum to “The Indo-Europeanization of the world from a Central Asian homeland: New approaches, paradigms and insights from our research publications on Ancient India” which was published in Journal of Social Science Studies, Macrothink Institute, Volume 3, Number 1 in 2015

Sujay Rao Mandavilli

Abstract

In the main paper, we explained how the Indo-Europeanization of the world may have happened from the Central Asian homeland using maps and diagrams. We also proposed the ‘Ten modes of linguistic transformations associated with Human migrations’, and the approaches we proposed were perhaps vastly superior to existing approaches. This addendum offers additional tips which could help depict the transformation of Pre-Indo-European languages to Indo-European languages in various geographical areas. Our paper along with this addendum could lead to a revolution in human knowledge, with a better understanding of cultural and social paradigms, and benefit scholars and students of Indo-European studies across nationalities. The Indo-European question is not as vexatious as it seems. It can easily be tackled and solved in the twenty-first century if the proposals in the main paper and this addendum are adhered to. For this, scholars from different parts of the world must work together as explained. There is already a welcome change as people from different regions of the world have begun to show interest in this issue in the past couple of decades. For this, however, nationalism and region-centrism which is a troubling sign, must be eschewed by scholars across the world, and a global outlook adopted. To accomplish a readership of this addendum, reading the main part of this paper, “The Indo-Europeanization of the world from a Central Asian homeland: New approaches, paradigms and insights from our research publications on Ancient India” which was published in Journal of Social Science Studies, Macrothink Institute, Volume 3, Number 1 in 2015 is mandatory.

Summary of the main paper

The Indo-European question can trace its roots to Sir William Jones' discovery that the Indo-Aryan languages spoken in India were related to those in Europe and perhaps had a common ancestor, commonly called Proto Indo-European or PIE. Although some missionaries such as Filippo Sassetti and others such as Lord Monboddo had noticed the similarities between European and Indian languages much earlier than Jones, it was Jones who is accredited with having laid the foundation for Indo-European studies across the world. This interest was due to the sheer complexity of this problem, the vast distances involved across much of Europe, India and Iran, and the fact that many Indo-European languages like Sanskrit were highly influential in their respective regions. Jones' ideas found support among other scholars, and the foundation was eventually laid for comparative philology and historical linguistics in the years that followed.¹

In the main paper, we had proposed the Six Phases of the Indo-Europeanization of the World as follows (a) Phase A: The spread of various dialects and languages comprising what we called Base Indo European from the Indo-European homeland as a result of migrations at different points in time, and resultant linguistic transformations in regions outside the IE homeland. (b) Phase B: Billiard like extensions. This phase would comprise the Indo-Europeanization of Europe, and the spread of Sanskrit in India influencing near eastern languages, Dravidian and other languages. This may have happened with or without human migrations. (c) Phase C: Tertiary extensions. This phase would comprise extensions like the spread of Sanskrit into South East Asia from India at a later date. (d) Phase D: This phase would comprise the spread of IE languages in recent times due to migrations from Europe to the New World. (e) Phase E: This phase would comprise the spread of IE as a secondary language due to colonialism in places such as Africa and Asia. (f) Phase F: This phase would comprise the spread of IE languages in the 20th and 21st centuries due to current globalization trends.²³

Different models explaining the Indo-Europeanization of different parts of the world have been proposed by various scholars over the years. One of them is the unlikely Anatolian model proposed by the British scholar Colin Renfrew which involves the spread of agriculturalists from the Asia Minor region also known to scholars as Anatolia from 7000 BC or later. The Near Eastern model is another model supported by a small number of scholars. Among the proponents of this model are the linguists Tamaz Gamkrelidze, Vyacheslav Ivanov and Stanislav Grigoriev. According to this model, the homeland is located south of the Caucasus, and Indo-European expansions are believed to have taken place from this region. Marija Gimbutas' homeland which is a part of the much more widely-accepted and probably correct Kurgan hypothesis or the Pontic- Caspian model, and posits a homeland including regions to the East of the Caspian Sea in the steppes and this includes Georgia, Azerbaijan and Armenia, and parts of Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan as well. We proposed that the PIE (or base Indo-European) may not have been a single language or just a group of dialects, but perhaps a language group in itself, spoken over a large region and this could account for differences in the PIE among different scholars. These languages could then have spread to Europe and other regions in Asia at different points in time, accompanied in most cases by small migrations, and leading to assimilation and acculturation in outlying regions in a bidirectional two-way process. Migrations involving very

¹ On the internal classification of Indo-European languages: survey[*] Václav Blažek

² Syncretism and Acculturation in Ancient India: A new Nine phase acculturation model explaining the process of transfer of power from the Harappans to the Indo Aryans Part One Sujay Rao Mandavilli ICFAI Journal of history and culture January 2009

³ Syncretism and Acculturation in Ancient India: A new Nine phase acculturation model explaining the process of transfer of power from the Harappans to the Indo Aryans Part Two Sujay Rao Mandavilli ICFAI Journal of history and culture January 2010

large distances may not be warranted in most cases and a domino model involving a chain reaction may be proposed, and would most probably be accurate.^{4 5}

Therefore, the languages of Europe, North India and Iran may have not been linear descendants of the PIE as assumed but may have only been heavily influenced by them or may have evolved as a result of a more complex interplay of linguistic forces. IE languages, would in many cases been viewed as culturally superior in most regions to allow them to spread, or would have been associated with superior technology such as horse riding. This is due to the fact that migrants could only have been small in number, and could not have replaced the native populations of different regions in any case. In other cases, transformations could have happened due to historical accidents as evidenced by the transformation of Harappan India to Post-Harappan India.

While developing models, scholars would therefore naturally need to bear in mind the fact that migrations would have been small in most cases, given the small populations of the IE homeland. This would pre-empt simplistic models in most cases. Therefore, replacements would have been cultural or linguistic rather than genetic, and wholesale replacements of languages would also have been unlikely. Scholars will also need to identify triggers or motives for migration as humans tend not to migrate unless absolutely required. Consequently, large scale migrations would be harder to justify. We had formulated these as a part of the 'Ten golden rules'

We propose the following ten scenarios of linguistic transformations in this context:

- (a) Complete replacement or Annihilation: This would be a very simplistic view, and one that may be practically rare and inapplicable to most situations. Such scenarios have however, been witnessed in a few cases examples being the USA, where native languages were more or less annihilated by IE languages such as English.
- (b) Linguistic Sub-ordination: Linguistic Sub-ordination (non-IE languages subordinated to IE languages) was another concept we had discussed in our previous paper, and may be relatively more common than annihilation.
- (c) Roller-ball model (Single loop): In this scenario, an alien language spreads up to a certain point in time, loses its original form, and is influenced by the languages native to the region.
- (d) Roller-ball model (Double or Multiple loop): This is an extension of the Single Loop Roller-ball model where both groups of languages keep influencing each other as was observed in case of the rather complex transformation of Harappan India to Post-Harapan India.
- (e) Extended Roller-ball model (Roller-ball model combined with Billiard-like extensions): In this model, a language spreads up to a certain point in time through one of the methods above, and subsequently spreads through cultural diffusion at later points in time to other outlying regions.
- (f) Assimilation: The language or languages of the immigrants die out completely over a period of time, leaving behind no trace. (Local languages may however be influenced) This is in stark contrast to the idea of annihilation of languages, and may happen under rare or special circumstances.
- (g) Cultural diffusion without transhumance movements or 'Pure Acculturation': This may be relatively rare from the perspective of Indo-European studies even though they may be observed in the 21st century.

⁴ Twenty-first century clouds over Indo-European homelands: J P Mallory Queens University, Belfast

⁵ THE INDO-EUROPEAN FAMILY — THE LINGUISTIC EVIDENCE by Brian D. Joseph, The Ohio State University

h) Transhumance movements without linguistic change: In this scenario, there is minimal to no interaction between speakers and both languages continue to exist in parallel.

(i) Lateral influences: Lateral influences are not just an interesting theoretical possibility: they have actually been observed in the context of Indo-European studies. I.e., lateral influences between Persia and India which played a vital role in the development of Vedic Sanskrit and the RV.

(j) Variants or combinations of the above scenarios may also be pervasive in the real-world and as such it is only expected that scholars will take cues from the above scenarios. ⁶

This approach always talks about two or more streams of languages and adds several more dimensions to the issue, including mandating a knowledge of local histories and issues.

Any discussion will be a non-starter unless accompanied by a thorough knowledge of the local history such as the history of different periods of England, France or Germany, (including different historical models, if applicable) (For example, even though England became inhabited 800000 years ago, one notable phase of Indo-Europeanization is the Roman conquest of 43 CE till the 5th century CE, followed by Anglo-Saxon migrations, predating the birth of Old English; however there were believed to have been earlier migrations from Europe around 2500 BCE from the Bell Beaker culture which may have been related to the cultures from the steppes (Olalde et al. (2018)) (In France, Gaulish was a Celtic language (already IE) which was subsequently further transformed by foreign rule of the Greeks, Romans and Carthaginians. However, Pre-IE languages such as Aquitanian were also present) (In Italy, Etruscan culture flourished from 800 BC, and they probably spoke a Non-IE language. Greek dialects began to reach Italy in the few centuries before the Christian era, and Greek was spoken by the elite well into the Roman period. During the Roman period, Latin (which was later used by the elites in many parts of the world) became popular, though its origin is obscure) culture, languages both ancient and modern, and knowledge of any other extraneous factors impacting such issues such as the pre-researched history of languages. The pre-researched history of languages may be used as a starting point, but may be modified based on the researcher's inputs and conclusions. A familiarity with linguistic and archaeological evidence pertaining to the area is also mandatory. However, a scholar is not required to acquire proficiency in a large number of languages. What is required is a collaborative effort between scholars of backgrounds across cultures in different parts of Europe and in Iran and India (and different specializations within a culture), in addition to a core centralized team, such that this kind of a collaboration leads to a rapid increase in knowledge. ⁷

The Tree Model:

The Tree Model was popularized by August Schleicher around 1860. In its simplest form, the 'Tree model' consists of a 'Proto-Language' (Proven or assumed), say 'A' branching into languages 'B', 'C' and 'D'. 'B', 'C' and 'D' in turn may have further branches. Anybody who is familiar with our work will agree that this antiquated model is too simplistic to have any value in the real-world, and in the context of Indo-European studies.

The Wave Model

The Wave Model was first proposed by Hugo Schuchardt and Johannes Schmidt around 1870 as an alternative to the 'Tree model'. Under the Wave Model, an instance of language change arises usually from within a geographical region, and from there spreads to adjacent speaker groups. The

⁶ History of Civilizations of Central Asia, Volume I and II (UNESCO Publishing)

⁷ Cambridge Textbooks in Linguistics: Sociolinguistics Second Edition R.A Hudson Cambridge University Press 2001

propagation of the change is therefore like a 'wave' which expands away from its centre as the new feature is adopted by other languages usually in the region." The Wave Model may not address all scenarios arising from Human migrations, and cannot be adopted in unmodified form.

The Ten dimensions of the Indo-European debate

Needless to say, the Indo-European debate has also been multi-faceted, and Harald Haarmann classifies issues associated with this debate into the following seven dimensions:

(a) The Economic dimension: This dimension deals with economic issues. For example, the transition from foraging to pastoralist subsistence.

(b) The Socio-Political dimension: For example, the emergence of stratified society and statehood in South Eastern Europe.

(c) The Ethnic dimension: this dimension deals with interaction between people of various ethnicities during the process of Indo-Europeanization.

(d) The Cultural dimension: this dimension deals with a fusion of different cultural traditions during the process of Indo-Europeanization.

(e) The Linguistic dimension: this dimension deals with language shifts arising due to the process of Indo-Europeanization. Here, a layer-by-layer approach needs to be followed. For example, Hindi, which is a modern Indo-Aryan language was greatly influenced by Persian as well during the medieval era. Again, spoken language needs to be differentiated from written language. We had observed that the spread of writing and the introduction of alphabets in Indo-Aryan languages in India followed a completely different path.

(f) The Visual-artistic dimension: The spread of visual imagery representing Indo-European traits forms a part of this dimension.

(g) The Mythical dimension: The study of Indo-European Gods and Goddesses forms a part of this dimension.

To this, we propose to add the following three dimensions:

(a) The Archaeological dimension: This dimension deals with all types of archaeological evidence associated with the spread of Indo-European

(b) The Technological dimension: This dimension deals the spread of technology such as the use of chariots and Iron in specific contexts – inevitably, both these technologies did not exist in the IE homeland.

(c) The Genetic dimension: This dimension deals with the Genetic evidence associated with the Indo-European problem.

Research on each of these dimensions must be carried out independently as there is little possibility of a complete overlap of issues associated with all the above dimensions. For example, the spread of language may not happen in tandem with the spread of technology.

We also propose the following colour scheme for greater clarity. (1) The Red arrows will represent the constituents of Base Indo-European moving out of the homeland usually, though not always in conjunction with human migrations. Where dates are available, information will be provided alongside the arrows. (2) The Blue arrows will represent Billiard like extensions. These may be at several levels.

For example, Sanskrit and Prakrits influenced Dravidian languages. Secondly, Sanskrit may have spread to South-East Asia from South India at a later period of time. (3) The Green arrows will represent tertiary extensions. Examples of these are the Indo-Europeanization of North America, South America and Australasia in modern times.

Different types of linguistic transformations may also be represented using different icons, and our proposals are as below. These will be useful while preparing diagrams and other kinds of visual depictions.

1 Complete replacement or Annihilation: Two triangles pointing upwards

2 Linguistic Sub-ordination: Single triangle pointing upwards

3 Roller-ball model (Single loop) ∞ (Single sigma)

4 Roller-ball model (Double or Multiple loop) $\infty\infty$ (double sigma)

5 Extended Roller-ball model (Roller-ball model combined with Billiard-like extensions) Billiard-like extensions shown through distinct arrows of the appropriate colour

6 Assimilation: Single triangle pointing downwards

7 Cultural diffusions without transhumance movements or 'Pure Acculturation' Arrows with dotted lines

8 Transhumance movements without linguistic change: Crossed circle Or =

9 Lateral influences: Arrows of the appropriate colour

10 Various combinations of the above scenarios: Uses the relevant icons sequentially

11 Unresolved: Uses a question mark

Changes in approaches and focus areas

Also note the following (a) Identifying the IE homeland or *Urheimat* can be much more reliably be done once the methods and approaches presented in the main paper are followed. (b) The major focus going forward should be identifying and analysing how linguistic transformations took place in various outlying regions and identifying as many new scenarios from across the world as possible. Thus, several new modes of linguistic transformation may be identified, and added to the body of knowledge. An inductive or nomothetic approach may be followed. (c) Another major focus should be identifying the characteristics of various components of Base Indo-European using the various approaches – or combinations of the various approaches - laid down in the main paper. (d) Another major paradigm shift would a globalized approach with scholars from many regions in the world participating, and the key principles for the above have been laid bare in the main paper as well as our earlier ones. (e) Another major paradigm shift would be multi-disciplinary approaches, and the key principles for this have been laid bare in our earlier papers. ⁸

Formation of language groups

Language groups may have been the result of more permanent natural barriers such as mountains, large rivers, seas and oceans which may have led to a separation between two linguistic groups. In some other cases, they may have been a result of extraneous factors such as human migrations leading

⁸ General Linguistics and Indo-European Reconstruction Frederik Kortlandt

to linguistic transformations in a given region. Scholars are well-advised to study the formation of language groups more closely taking into account the various forms of evidence discussed in this paper, as well as political and historical factors. These may prove to be veritable jackpots and could yield rich cues on the origin and spread of languages. In many cases, however, classification of languages into language groups may be erroneous and subject to the whims of scholars, and future scholars need to bear this in mind.⁹

Proto-languages and language groups

The idea of a hypothetical proto-language being an ancestor of a family of languages, may also be an over-simplification by today's standards and may be linked to the antiquated tree model. The idea of a language splitting up into many different languages without any apparent underlying reason, seems not only highly over-simplistic, but also flawed. Some early scholars erroneously believed that all the world's languages could be traced to a handful of proto-languages. Readers are urged to read our main paper and our paper on the origin of languages (Epochal polygenesis approach) as well for further clarity.¹⁰

Languages can likewise die out, but scholars need to bear in mind the fact that this is usually a slow process: this aspect needs to be borne in mind while studying linguistic transformations due to migrations as well. Language extinction can occur only when the language has no competent language speakers and when the language falls into disuse. This naturally would be a slow process.

Use of Ethnography

The term 'Ethnography' is a combination of two Greek words, namely: 'ethnos' which means 'folk' or 'peoples' and 'grapho' which means 'to write'. Ethnography is therefore, a detailed narrative of communities and their lifestyles with the objective of long-term knowledge generation, and is sometimes referred to as a detailed and a structured 'portrait of a people'. Ethnography therefore seeks to provide a detailed and a scientific study of or a group, community, society or culture. Ethnography also typically involves a prolonged interaction with different communities, and is a systematic description of a contemporary culture through extensive and intensive fieldwork in a wholly natural context or setting. Ethnographic studies usually focus on a particular community or group, and specific aspects of that group. Ethnography may be used as a part of IE studies to understand how languages change and die by targeting specific languages, or specific groups of languages, and studying speaker behaviour, preferences and attitudes. Ethnography may likewise be used in various fields of linguistics. One drawback is that such studies are of a longer duration, and for this we may propose 'perpetual ethnography' which involves the study of the same issue at different points in time by the same team or by different teams. This would be critical for a long-term analysis.

Our work only covers linguistic changes arising out of Human migrations. For a more comprehensive perspective, linguistic changes arising out of other scenarios also need to be taken into account, although although this must be left to other scholars. Linguistic change not arising due to human migrations, needs to be studied at a greater level of detail by other scholars or linguists not specializing in the spread of IE. This would have some impact on language change in the long-term as the Indo-Europeanization of the world was typically a slow process. The two, when taken together, would constitute of proposed replacement for the Tree model and the Wave model.

⁹ Alexandre Fran_ cois. *Trees, Waves and Linkages: Models of Language Diversification*. Bower, Claire; Evans, Bethwyn. *The Routledge Handbook of Historical Linguistics*, Routledge, pp.161189, 2014, 978-0-41552-789-7.

¹⁰ *Trees, Waves and Linkages: Models of Language Diversification* Alexandre Francois

Methods of performing analysis

There can be potentially several different approaches of performing analysis within a sub-branch of IE languages, and we list a few of them below. In all these approaches, the other concepts introduced in the main paper as well as in this addendum must be rigorously adhered to:

Outside in approach based on the geographical distance from the IE homeland (FAFA). Per this approach, the IE language which is farthest from the IE homeland is analysed first, and analysis is done backwards, such that the oldest IE language or base Indo-European is eventually reached. However, an analysis of linkages with other languages such as non-IE languages can be done in any direction. This approach can also be adopted in conjunction with other approaches for different IE streams. Per this approach, modern IE languages of North America and South America such as English, Portuguese and Spanish can be taken up for analysis first, and analysis can proceed backwards to their respective antecedents in Europe.

Analysing youngest languages first (YOFA): Per this approach, the IE language that is youngest is taken up for analysis first. In order to accomplish this, a basic analysis ranking various IE languages in the order of age may need to be done before a detailed analysis can be carried out. Again, an analysis of linkages with other languages such as Non-IE languages can be done in any direction. This approach can also be adopted in conjunction with other approaches for different IE streams. Per this approach again, modern IE languages of North America and South America such as English, Portuguese and Spanish can be taken up for analysis first, and analysis can proceed backwards to their respective antecedents in Europe.

Inside out approach: Per this approach, languages nearest to the IE homeland are analysed first, and analysis is done outwards. Again, an analysis of linkages with other languages such as Non-IE languages can be done in any direction. This approach can also be adopted in conjunction with other approaches for different IE streams.

Oldest languages first analysed: Per this approach, which is diametrically opposed to the YOFA approach the oldest IE language is analysed first, and younger languages are then analysed in a sequential fashion. Again, an analysis of linkages with other languages such as Non-IE languages can be done in any direction. This approach can also be adopted in conjunction with other approaches for different IE streams. Per this approach, languages such as the partially reconstructed PIE (refer the main paper), or Hittite (being the oldest attested IE language, albeit by a slender margin) and Vedic Sanskrit may be analysed first followed by younger languages.

Random Analysis or bi-directional analysis within a stream of IE languages: Per this approach, analysis is done in a random order subject to the availability of data. Per a variant of this approach, analysis is done bidirectionally from a central point and subject to clarity or availability of data, such that missing linkages are closed progressively.

Combination of various methods: Per this approach, different approaches amongst those listed above, are adopted for different streams of IE languages, while adopting other modes of analysis for peripheral studies such as a linkage with Non-IE languages.

In all these approaches, relationships between current Indo-European languages and older IE languages, relationships between parent and daughter languages, and relationship between IE languages and non-IE languages, and a geographical chain or dispersal analysis must be followed, while always maintaining dates. Thus, the timing of influence or linguistic transformation must be shown, and must be derived based on a knowledge of local history or histories and historical models.

If any along with the history of languages in the region, and a corroboration between the two. An example of the latter was our model showing the transformation of Harappan India to Post-Harappan India. Influences may be short-lived or prolonged and these may also be depicted suitably. If there are multiple influences at different points in time, these must also be shown.

Estimating the timing of influence: This can be done based on whether basic words were present or whether advanced vocabulary were included in the daughter language. For example, in the case of Vedic Sanskrit, only basic words are traceable to the PIE, and more advanced vocabulary are indigenous in origin. This would imply that the split up happened at a very early date, and long before the RV was compiled. Likewise, an analysis of different parts of speech may be done. In the case of Vedic Sanskrit, it may be observed that pronouns and basic nouns are mostly of IE origin while more complex nouns, verbs, adjectives and adverbs are of indigenous origin. This would imply that the split up happened very early, again long before the RV was compiled. A study of the word order (VSO,SVO or flexible word order) would also be required. Since the word order cannot change from parent to daughter languages under ordinary circumstances, this would illustrate the type of influence. If the word order was changes, it would indicate a transformation rather than a complete replacement. Other linguistic features such as the presence or absence of a neuter gender in a particular IE language vis a vis other related languages, may also be one of the factors involved in an analysis. A study of isolates such as Brahui in present-day Pakistan may also be carried out along with the study of the influences IE languages had on such languages. These approaches would be somewhat superior to an analysis of the substratum of IE languages which can throw up erroneous results. Conventional classification of languages into Genealogical Classification (Languages are grouped by diachronic relatedness into language families), Typological Classification. (Languages are grouped into language types on the basis of formal criteria, according to their similarities in grammatical structure) Areal Classification (areal features are elements shared by languages or dialects in a geographic area, particularly when such features are not descended from a proto-language, or, common ancestor language) may also serve as a rough guide in assessing linguistic transformations.

Annotated bar and rod diagram

The resultant diagram would be known as the Annotated bar and rod diagram which would be vastly superior to Tree models and wave modes. As discussed, these would be tied a regions history or histories as well as complex historical models pertinent to a region. The following are the key features of this diagram:

- Lists cross influences by means of connectors
- Lists type of cross influences. Notations for the “Ten modes of linguistic transformation” are used. Additional modes of linguistic transformation can be listed by other scholars as a part of their research, and suitable notations developed.
- Lists degree of cross influences, along with the nature of cross-influences, if possible. This can be shown by modulating the thickness of lines
- Lists timing of cross influences along with dates
- If cross-influences are prolonged, these may be annotated as such along with a range of dates
- The diagram is dated throughout, and history of development of languages along with cross-influences is dated
- Relationship between IE languages and non- IE languages may be shown separately, if required
- Split up of languages may be shown if applicable, while avoiding over-simplifications

- The transformation of pre-IE languages to IE languages is shown wherever applicable as a separate stream so that the history of Pre-IE (i.e. to be transformed languages) is also shown where relevant. (Refer our model on transformation of Harappan Indian to post-Harappan India, for example)
- IE languages may be shown as horizontal lines . For example, the PIE, Old Avestan and Persian may be shown as parallel lines with connectors as described here.
- Pre-IE Languages may be marked differently on horizontal lines
- Dates may be shown on the x-axis both for the pre-Christian era and the Christian era
- Influences may be shown as vertical lines perpendicular to the horizontal lines, and elaborated as discussed above. These vertical lines connect two IE languages, one of which is the older IE language and the other, which is transformed.
- The thickness of these lines can show the degree of influence
- Appropriate notations are used for the type of linguistic transformation (Refer the main paper)
- The colour scheme delineated in the main paper may be used (Red arrows, blue arrows and green arrows)
- The diagram is annotated with suitable explanations and suitable explanations are provided throughout by means of additional notes or call out boxes
- Vocabulary pertaining to each period of cultural transformation may be shown in an annexure
- This diagram must cover all IE languages eventually, though this would be a laborious and time-consuming process. This may even take up to a century or more if an earnest effort is made, and involve scholars from different parts of the world.
- The common name for each language is shown alongside
- All languages influenced by IE languages may also be shown E.g., Munda even if they are not classified as IE languages. This may make the diagram somewhat clumsy, and so, separate diagrams may be used for this purpose.
- If the Horizontal line terminates abruptly, it refers to the death of a language.
- The diagram may be split up if it becomes too unwieldy or clumsy and the appropriate linkages inserted by means of connectors.
- Open and unresolved issues may be marked as such, and suitably annotated.
- At the discretion of the researcher, unimportant or minor languages may be omitted from the analysis or shown in separate diagrams.
- Likewise, minor issues such as dialect levelling may be omitted or explained through annotations.
- The nature of use of the language whether used in daily speech, used by the elite, or liturgical may also be indicated.
- A variant of this diagram is drawn on a map as was shown in the main paper. In this case, different regional maps may be used, and linked by means of connectors. In this variant, the spread of IE is drawn along geographical regions, making it much more intuitive.

Conclusion

The Indo-European question is not as vexatious as it seems. It can easily be tackled and solved in the twenty-first century if the proposals in the main paper and this addendum are adhered to. For this, scholars from different parts of the world must work together as explained. There has already been a welcome change in the past two decades as people from different regions of the world have begun to show interest in this issue in the past couple of decades. While no compelling models have been presented as yet, scholars from other parts of the world have at least begun to question earlier models. For this endeavour to be taken to a higher level, however, nationalism and region-centrism

which is a troubling sign, must be eschewed by scholars across the world, and a global outlook adopted. This is easier said than done, however, as few scholars may possess the knowledge of diverse disciplines and geographies that this issue warrants. However, collaboration, trust and a spirit of bonhomie can make a world of a difference and yield rich rewards.

